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Trademark Applications in Italian Regions

Trademark applications in Italian regions have grown on average by 32.35% between 2018 and 2023. The European Innovation Scoreboard (EIS) calculates trademark applications per billion of GDP in Italian regions. The data consist of a ratio between the number of trademark applications filed with the European Union Intellectual Property Office (EUIPO) and the Gross Domestic Product in Purchasing Power Standards. Trademarks are an important indicator of innovation, especially for the service sector. The EU trademark grants its holder a uniform right applicable in all member states of the European Union through a single procedure that simplifies trademark policy at the European level. It fulfills the three essential functions of a trademark it identifies the origin of goods and services, guarantees consistent quality through the company's commitment to consumers, and serves as a form of communication, a basis for advertising and publicity. The data are available for the 20 Italian regions between 2018 and 2023.

Trend of Trademark Applications in Italian Regions in 2023. The data show that Veneto is the region with the highest number of trademark applications, with a value of 168.48, indicating a particularly active entrepreneurial environment and perhaps a greater propensity for innovation and protection of their products and services. Conversely, Calabria has the lowest number of applications with only 53.23, which could indicate lower industrial activity or a lesser inclination towards innovation and legal protection of their intellectual property in the region. This data could also result from economic barriers or a lack of information about the importance of trademarks. Lombardy and Emilia-Romagna also show high numbers, with 157.93 and 153.44 respectively, confirming their role as economic engines of Northern Italy with a strong concentration of advanced industries and services. Lombardy, in particular, hosts a large number of fashion and design companies, sectors where trademark registration is crucial for protecting intellectual property. Also noteworthy are the cases of Trentino-Alto Adige and Tuscany, with 146.12 and 141.72 respectively. These figures reflect a solid industrial base and a strong regional identity that values and seeks to protect its peculiarities through trademarks. Campania and Puglia, with 111.94 and 115.98 respectively, also show significant activity. This could reflect increasing economic dynamism in these regions, traditionally less industrialized than the north, but which have seen a rise in entrepreneurial initiatives in recent years. In central Italy, Lazio stands at 97.06, which is relatively high but not at the levels of Northern Italy. This can be attributed to the different economic composition of the region, which, while being the seat of Rome and thus the government and many institutions, may not have the same concentration of manufacturing or high-tech activities. Regions with values around or below 80, such as Liguria, Sardinia, and Valle d'Aosta, with 81.19, 83.99, and 85.32 respectively, may reflect more limited economies in terms of industrial variety or fewer opportunities or needs for trademark registration. Further analysis is necessary to fully understand the causes behind these differences, including factors

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such as regional GDP, level of industrialization, education, and access to information on intellectual property rights. However, these data provide a clear overview of how various Italian regions are adopting legal tools for the protection of innovations and investments in trademarks, indicating significant differences in the economic and entrepreneurial fabric of the country.

Trend of Trademark Applications in Italian Regions between 2018 and 2023. The region that has shown the most significant percentage growth is Sardinia, with an impressive increase of 164.617% in trademark applications, rising from 31.740 in 2018 to 83.990 in 2023. This huge leap could indicate an accelerated development of regional economic activity or greater awareness of the importance of trademarks. Apulia and Sicily have also recorded very high increases, with 90.506% and 90.021% respectively. These figures indicate a vibrant awakening of entrepreneurial activity in these regions, traditionally less industrialized than Northern Italy, but now seem to be focusing heavily on the protection and enhancement of their products and services. Conversely, Veneto, despite being one of the most industrialized regions with the highest number of trademark applications in 2023, has shown the lowest percentage growth, only 6.253%. This could suggest that the region already had a high level of trademark-related activity in 2018, with less room for substantial increases. Among the northern regions, Lombardy continued to show solid growth with a 25.895% increase in applications, consolidating its position as one of the country's main economic and industrial centers. This reflects the region's significant industrial base and proactive approach to intellectual property protection. Emilia-Romagna and Trentino-Alto Adige both recorded moderate increases, with 16.173% and 25.541% respectively. These figures reflect the stability of their mature and diversified economies, which continue to invest in trademark protection as a tool for competitiveness. In central Italy, Lazio showed an increase of 45.249%, likely driven by the concentration of tech start-ups and growing entrepreneurial activity in the capital, Rome. Overall, these data suggest that the south and the islands are catching up with the north, traditionally more active in terms of trademark applications.

Trend of Trademark Applications in Italian Macro-Regions in 2023. The analysis of trademark applications in the Italian macro-regions—South, North, and Center—between 2018 and 2023 offers an interesting perspective on the dynamics of the country's entrepreneurial fabric. The absolute and percentage variation of these applications underscores significant regional differences and growth trends that reflect an evolution in the approach to intellectual property protection and innovation. The South has shown the most marked percentage growth among the three areas, with an increase of 60.69% in trademark applications, rising from 51.34 in 2018 to 82.5 in 2023. This significant increase, with an absolute change of 31.16, is indicative of a vigorous economic awakening. It could be due to various factors, including government incentives for startups, increased entrepreneurial activity, and strengthened commercial and technological infrastructure that have enabled broader penetration of national and international markets. The Center recorded a 30.97% increase in applications, with a jump from 90.73 to 118.83. The absolute increase of 28.1 reflects robust growth, testifying to an entrepreneurial environment that continues to expand strongly. This region benefits from a geographical position that facilitates commercial interactions between northern and southern Italy, as well as a concentration of high-tech industries and research institutes that promote innovation. The North, despite being the area with the highest number of applications in both 2018 and 2023, showed the lowest percentage growth, at 19.14%. Although the absolute increase of 20.15 is substantial, the lower percentage compared to the other areas suggests a possible market maturation or saturation in new trademark registrations. Northern Italy, with its advanced and established economies, might be

in a stabilization phase where trademark application growth becomes less exponential but more sustained and qualitatively oriented towards niche innovation and specialization. Overall, these data highlight a transformation in the Italian industrial and commercial landscape, with a rapidly rising South seeking to close the historical gap with the North. The implications of these trends are profound, indicating not only diversified economic growth but also a growing awareness of the importance of intellectual property protection as a lever for competitiveness and innovation. Moreover, the dynamics among regions suggest that incentive policies and support for entrepreneurship and innovation may have played a crucial role in this evolution, fostering an environment where businesses are more inclined to invest in trademarks to stand out in an increasingly crowded global market.

North-South Divide. The analysis of trademark applications in the Italian macro-regions between 2018 and 2023 suggests an interesting dynamic between the North and the South of the country, with clear signs of a reduction in the traditional economic and industrial divide between these areas. Although there is still a difference in the total volume of applications, with the North continuing to outperform the South, growth trends indicate that the South is gaining significant ground. The South recorded a 60.69% increase in trademark applications, growing from 51.34 in 2018 to 82.5 in 2023. This percentage jump is markedly higher than the 19.14% recorded by the North in the same period. Such robust growth in the South could be interpreted as the result of several positive factors improved economic conditions, government incentives aimed at stimulating innovation and entrepreneurship, and a greater propensity of local businesses to protect their brands and innovations through trademark registration. In contrast, the North shows more moderate growth, with an absolute increase of 20.15 in trademark applications, suggesting a phase of consolidation rather than rapid expansion. This could be due to the fact that the North already has a well-developed industrial and commercial fabric, with many established companies that may have less immediate need for new trademark registrations compared to startups or expanding businesses in the South. The Center, with a 30.97% increase, positions itself at an intermediate level, reflecting a more balanced situation between established industries and new entrepreneurial initiatives. Although the volume of trademark applications in the South remains lower than in the North, the growth rate highlights a dynamism that could lead to a progressive reduction in the economic and industrial gap between the two macro-regions. This phenomenon is significant because trademark protection is often indicative of greater economic maturity and a business strategy oriented towards long-term growth and innovation. However, it is important to note that the presence of a gap is not measured solely by the volume of trademark applications but also through indicators such as regional GDP, investment levels in R&D, education, and access to financial and international markets. Furthermore, differences in the types of industries prevalent in each region can influence these numbers, with the North potentially having more companies in high-tech or capital-intensive sectors that traditionally register more trademarks.

Economic Policies. The increase in trademark applications is a significant indicator of economic vitality and innovation in a region. Economic policies to stimulate this type of activity in Italian regions can play a crucial role in attracting investments, promoting innovation, and protecting intellectual property. An effective strategy requires an integrated approach involving local and national governments, research institutes, and the private sector. One of the most direct policies to stimulate the increase in trademark applications is to offer tax incentives to companies that invest in R&D and trademark registration. This can include tax deductions, tax credits for research and

development activities, and specific grants to cover the costs of trademark registration. These incentives can reduce the economic burden for startups and SMEs, encouraging the protection of their innovative developments. Many businesses, especially small and medium-sized enterprises, are not fully aware of the benefits of trademark registration and intellectual property protection. Awareness campaigns and educational seminars organized in collaboration with local chambers of commerce can increase awareness of intellectual property rights and their impact on business competitiveness. Establishing or enhancing local intellectual property offices to offer technical assistance, legal advice, and administrative support for trademark registration. These offices could work in synergy with universities and research centers to facilitate technology transfer and the commercialization of innovations. Improving digital infrastructures to make the trademark registration process simpler and less time-consuming. This includes the digitization of registration services and the creation of online platforms that allow easy interaction between entrepreneurs and the trademark office. Stimulating partnerships between academia and industries to promote applied research and innovation. This can lead to the development of new products and services that need protection through trademarks. Moreover, these collaborations can be incentivized through specific funding and business incubation programs that facilitate the commercialization of innovations. Promoting the creation of regional clusters that connect companies, universities, and research centers in specific sectors such as biotechnology, digital technologies, or advanced manufacturing. These clusters can benefit from dedicated support, including funds for intellectual property protection and the promotion of trademarks at the international level. Simplifying bureaucracy and regulations regarding trademark registration and intellectual property protection. A clear and simplified regulatory policy can significantly reduce the time and costs associated with trademark registration, making it more accessible for small and medium-sized enterprises. By encouraging the adoption of these policies, Italian regions can not only increase the number of trademark applications but also stimulate innovation and economic competitiveness. These interventions require coordinated commitment between various levels of government and the private sector, but they have the potential to significantly transform the country's industrial and entrepreneurial landscape.

Conclusions. Trademark applications have grown on average in Italian regions in the period between 2018 and 2023 by 32.35%, rising from 80.81 units to 106.95 units. At the macro-regional level, significant growth can be observed in Southern Italy with +31.16%, in Northern Italy with +19.14%, and in Central Italy with a value of +30.97%. However, looking at the 2023 data, a clear leadership of Northern Italy is evident, followed by Central Italy, while the South remains far behind. In 2023, the level of trademark applications in Southern Italy was equal to 65% of the corresponding value in Northern Italy.

Declarations

Data Availability Statement. The data presented in this study are available on request from the corresponding author.

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Appendix

Absolute and Percentage Change in Trademark Applications by Region, 2018 to 2023

Absolute and Percentage Change in Trademark Applications by Macro Region, 2018 to 2023

Trademark Applications by Region in Italy, 2023